

EFFECT OF PEER-ASSISTED MIND MAPPING STRATEGY ON HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS IN PHYSICS

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Abstract

Students develop their higher-order cognitive skills and conceptual understanding of content knowledge through science education. Problem-solving and collaboration are higher-order cognitive skills important for effective learning. Physics is a core science subject considered boring, uninteresting, and irrelevant to the real world. One of the reasons for this negative attitude toward physics is the lengthy mathematical derivation and use of these equations for solving physics numerical problems. The present study aimed to find the effect of peer-assisted mind-mapping strategy on students' problem-solving skills. The sample for this experimental design was 132 (70 boys and 62 girls) grade XI students. Subjects were assigned to intervention and nonintervention groups randomly. The intervention groups were treated with the peer-assisted mind mapping strategy and the without intervention groups with the lecture method. Both groups were post-tested to know the effect of the treatment. Researcher-made problem-solving test comprised 80 MCQs as an instrument to collect data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze data. The results concluded that the peer-assisted mind mapping strategy has a profound positive effect on the problem-solving skills and attitudes of intervention groups. The teachers should be encouraged to use a peer-assisted mind-mapping strategy in the teaching-learning process which may help students to enhance their problem-solving skills.

Keywords: Peer-Assisted Learning, Mind Mapping, Problem-Solving, Physics

INTRODUCTION

Man is fascinated by nature. His curious mind wants to find explanations for various phenomena occurring around him and also wants to solve the mysteries of the universe. Physics is the science that helps him in satisfying his curious mind. The main purpose of learning physics is how to predict and understand the behavior of matter and energy, that is to understand how the universe works (Giordano, 2010). Learning physics train students to acquire higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), like complex problem-solving, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication information (Foote, 2020) which guarantee the understanding of concepts, effective application of concepts, and better academic achievement. The conceptual understanding of physics is important because a few core concepts can explain many phenomena.

The participation of 4th grade Pakistani 4 students in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) resulted in poor performance where they were ranked second from the bottom in science and mathematics. It shows that students can

have a very basic and limited understanding of scientific concepts and knowledge of scientific facts (Halai, 2021; Akmal & Crawford, 2020). It shows the pathetic condition of science education in the country.

Problem-solving is higher-order cognitive skills. Problem-solving is the use of past experiences and prior knowledge to help in understanding the new disturbing situation and finding a solution to it. Woolfolk (2021) defines problem-solving as the formulation of new answers, beyond the simple application of prior learned principles to achieve a goal. Problem-solving is what happens when no explanation is understandable for the unknown phenomena. Science subjects and especially physics and mathematics offer various challenging situations to students. To work out them students, need to apply effective strategies.

Most of the students find physics boring, difficult, and irrelevant to the real world because they see physics as an isolated piece of information. They consider learning physics means memorization of information and problem-solving techniques that apply to highly particular situations. An effective instructional strategy changes students' views about physics and physics problem-solving and transforms them into efficient and active learners (Wieman & Perkins, 2005).

Krisak et al. (2014) suggest that the teaching of physics can only be made interesting and useful when traditional methods of teaching are replaced with innovative and interactive instructional strategies. This helps students better understand content knowledge, increases their attention, and enables them to work independently to reduce misconceptions. The driving force for this study was to introduce a student-centered effective learning strategy that would help to develop students' skills in using physics concepts and applying mathematical equations to make the physics problem-solving process more beneficial.

The interaction of all students with teachers and peers is necessary to test their thinking, to be challenged, to receive feedback, and to watch how others solve problems. When students interact and communicate with teachers and their peers, they find new ways of thinking and suggest solutions to their problems. Communicating with others makes students use, test, and sometimes change their thinking approaches (Woolfolk, 2021). During interaction with peers, students can disagree and challenge each other's ideas which result in allowing students to consider and craft the best ideas (Schunk, 2014).

Peer-assisted mind mapping strategy is based on the Russian psychologist Lev Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism. The core idea of social constructivism is that students learn a great deal from engaging in interactions with peers (Palincsar, 1998). The teacher's role is to facilitate and enable students to learn on their own and in groups. Students also facilitate each other's learning. According to Vygotsky social interactions and collaboration with peers is helpful for learning.

Some problems are challenging, and students are unable to find solutions to them even if every step is explained clearly. Vygotsky used the term zone of proximal development (ZPD), tasks that are too difficult for the child and can only be performed with the assistance of others like a teacher, parents, peers, or some other experienced person.

According to Vygotsky children learn very little when they work in their actual development level. To achieve the upper limits of ZPD the use of scaffolding is helpful for students. Scaffolding is the collective name of a variety of supportive techniques that can help students of any age accomplish difficult tasks in instructional settings (Ormrod, 2016; Santrock, 2011).

ZPD includes learning and problem-solving abilities included in ZPD can be learned for just beginning to emerge and develop. In this area, instruction is effective and is called “magic middle by Kathleen Berger. The ZPD of a student could be changed over time to solve problems face new challenges. In short, the promotion of cognitive development is possible only due to the emergence of new challenges (Woolfolk, 2021; Ormrod, 2016).

Mind Mapping was formalized as a strategy by Tony Buzon in the 1970s. It is an organizational thinking tool that uses central and important thoughts as keywords (Michalko, 2001). Mind mapping functions on the principle of “Radiant Thinking”. Mind maps are advance organizers which are presented learning and students use them to organize and interpret new information presented to them (Long et al., 2011). Important components of mind maps are colours, curved lines, symbols, words, and images. Boring material can be made interesting through mind maps using colourful diagram (Buzon, 2012). Polat et el. (2022) concluded in their study that mind-mapping activities have a positive effect on the development of the social skills of preschool children. Results from the study of motion and kinematics revealed that secondary school students taught through the mind-mapping teaching strategy performed better than those taught through the guided discovery method (Onah et al., 2022). Results of the study revealed that these strategies are very helpful in enhancing the learning, academic achievement, interest, and creativity of nursing students (Gok, 2014; Rezapour-Nasrabad, 2019; Rosciano, 2015). In science education through mind-mapping method, students’ concept learning, improvement of misunderstandings, academic achievement, and attitudes can be made better (Akinoglu & Yasar, 2007). The achievement of 8th-grade science students taught through mind mapping strategy had statistically significant effect on conceptual understanding and practical reasoning (Abi-El-Mona & Adb-El-Khalick, 2009). It was observed that like other visual tools, mind maps promote meaningful learning. It also found that the mind mapping method is very effective in improving the learning achievements of physics (Imaduddin & Utomo, 2012).

Research Question

Does the Peer-Assisted Mind Mapping Strategy help students in the development of their problem-solving skills in the subject of Physics?

Hypotheses of the Study

Hypotheses are intelligent and logical suppositions, reasonable guesses, and educated conjecture about how the research problem may be resolved. They provide a tentative explanation for a phenomenon under investigation and may direct thinking to possible sources of information that may help in resolving research problems. Hypotheses are essential ingredients in experimental research (Leedy & Ormrod, 2016; Cohen et al. 2018)

For answering the research question the given below hypotheses were tested.

H₀1: No significant difference in girls' problem-solving test scores between intervention and control groups before the treatment

H₀2: No significant difference in girls' problem-solving test scores of the intervention group between pre and post-treatment.

H₀3: No significant difference in boys' problem-solving test scores between the intervention and control group before the treatment

H₀4: No significant difference in boys' problem-solving test scores of the intervention group between pre and post-treatment

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In quantitative research, the researcher tried to define one or more variables of interest in advance and then quantified the observations of those variables. This study was a quantitative, and control group pretest-posttest experimental design. The independent variable was teaching strategy with two levels (peer-assisted mind mapping and traditional lecture method) and gender (male and female). The dependent variable was students' problem-solving skills. The sampled students were randomly assigned to intervention and control groups. The groups were equated on the pretest and were subjected to intervention. The intervention group was treated with a peer-assisted mind mapping strategy while the nonintervention group was taught through lecture method, for the same period. After the treatment period both groups were post-tested. Posttest scores were compared to determine the effectiveness of the treatment.

Population

The population of this study was the students of grade XI (science group) enrolled in Government Higher Secondary Schools Thand Koi and Government Girls Higher Secondary Schools Kunda of District Swabi during the academic session 2022-23.

Sample

A sample is a small part of the population that is representative of the population. Different sampling techniques are used for different designs. For this study using the Purposive sampling technique two schools Government Higher Secondary Schools Thand Koi and Government Girls Higher Secondary School Kunda were selected which had the required strength of students for the experiment. The sample was 132 (70 boys and 62 girls) grade XI students. participants were assigned to intervention and control groups using a simple random sampling technique.

Data Collection

The data was collected through researcher-made tests and an adopted questionnaire. For assessing the problem-solving skills of the students, the researcher prepared a test containing 80 Multiple Choice Questions (20 from each unit) with four options, Tests were

validated by the Senior Subject Specialist in Physics while its reliability was measured using the split-half method, and Cronbach’s alpha.

Analysis of Data

Inferential statistics independent sample t-test was used to compare the means of intervention and control groups and paired sample t-test was used to compare the means of intervention groups on pre and post-tests.

Table 1: Girls’ problem-solving test scores difference between intervention and control groups before the treatment

Groups	N	M	SD	SEM	t-value	Sig.	Cohen’d
Intervention	31	32.68	5.06	0.91	-0.070	0.944	0.02
Control	31	32.77	5.79	1.04			
Not Significant at $p > .05$							

It was evident from Table 1 in the comparison between intervention and control groups of girls before the treatment (with pre-test groups) for problem-solving test scores, there was a no significant difference between the intervention group ($N=31$, $M=32.68$, $SD=5.06$, $SEM=0.91$) and control group ($N=31$, $M=32.77$, $SD=5.79$, $SEM=1.04$), $t(60) = -0.070$, $p > 0.05$, $d = 0.02$. Thus, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis (H_01).

Table 2: Girls’ problem-solving test scores pre and post-treatment difference

Groups	M	SD	SEM	Correlation	Paired Differences			t-value	Sig.
					M	SD	SEM		
Pre	32.68	5.06	0.91	0.138	-17.55	9.38	1.68	-0.41	.00
Post	50.23	8.63	1.55						
Significant at $p < .05$									

Table 2 presented a comparison of girls’ problem-solving test scores of the intervention group before and after treatment (with pre-test groups) ($N = 31$) before treatment ($M = 32.68$, $SD = 5.06$ and $SEM = 0.91$) have lower mean score than after treatment ($M = 50.23$, $SD = 8.63$ and $SEM = 1.55$). Furthermore, a significant correlation was found between groups ($\alpha = 0.138$). The paired differences are shown ($M = -17.55$, $SD = 9.38$, $SEM = 1.68$), $t(60) = -10.42$, $p < .05$. This made the researcher unable to accept the null hypothesis (H_02).

Table 3: Boys’ problem-solving test scores difference between the intervention and control groups before the treatment

Groups	N	M	SD	SEM	t-value	Sig.	Cohen’d
Intervention	35	32.71	5.91	1.00	-0.051	0.960	0.01
Control	33	32.79	6.07	1.06			
Not Significant at $p > .05$							

Table 3 showed a comparison between the intervention and control groups of boys before the treatment (with pre-test groups) for problem-solving test scores in which a statistically non-significant difference can be seen for the intervention group ($N=35$, $M=32.71$, $SD=5.91$, $SEM=1.00$) and control group ($N=33$, $M=32.79$, $SD=6.07$, $SEM=1.06$), $t(66) = -0.051$, $p > .05$, $d = 0.01$. Thus, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis (H_03).

Table 4: Boys' problem-solving test scores pre and post-treatment difference

Groups	M	SD	SEM	Correlation	Paired Differences			t-value	Sig.
					M	SD	SEM		
Pre	32.71	5.92	1.00	0.21	-20.46	7.46	1.26	-16.22	.00
Post	53.17	5.92	1.00						
<i>Significant at $p < .05$</i>									

Table 4 displayed a comparison of problem-solving test scores of the intervention group before and after treatment (with pre-test groups) ($N = 35$), before treatment ($M = 32.71$, $SD = 5.92$, and $SEM = 1.00$) have smaller mean scores than after treatment ($M = 53.17$, $SD = 5.92$ and $SEM = 1.00$). Furthermore, a statistically significant correlation was found between groups ($\alpha = 0.21$). The paired differences are shown ($M = -20.46$, $SD = 7.46$, $SEM = 1.26$), $t(66) = -16.22$, $p < .05$. The researcher failed to accept the null hypothesis (H_04).

DISCUSSION

The physics problem-solving process is not just the search for the right equation and to plug in values but to manage and interpret information and reason logically, and to apply concepts and mathematical relations for the solution of these problems. Students can take an interest in problem-solving when working with other students in small groups.

Visual mapping can improve the problem-solving process by creating alternative solutions and options, revealing a previously unseen but appropriate action (Krasnic, 2012). Peer-assisted learning strategies are designed for students who can engage actively and work collaboratively with their peers to overcome their difficulties. Students can assist each other while solving physics problems. These strategies also help in building and developing social and communication skills. Students need to understand fundamental problem-solving rules to be able to deal with problems in new situations (Wenning & Vieyra, 2020). The researcher conducted an experimental study on the effect of peer-assisted mind mapping strategy on the problem-solving skills of higher secondary level students and from the data analysis it was observed that a significant difference was observed between the mean scores of the control and intervention groups which suggests that the implementation of this strategy improved the physics problem-solving skill of students. These results obtained are similar to the findings from the study of Akinoglu and Yasar (2007) who found that the use of mind mapping strategy affects the attitudes, academic achievement and concept learning of elementary level science students. The differences between the achievements of control and intervention groups were statistically significant on the posttests. It means that this strategy has a more positive effect on students' academic achievement, attitudes towards science studies classes, concept learning, and correction of misconception which helps in development of problem-solving skills. It also supports the study of Bin et al. (2022) where the strategy significantly improved the scientific research problem-solving ability, academic achievement, and reducing anxiety of college students. Similarly, the problem-solving skill of secondary school students improved when the mind-mapping strategy was incorporated into the teaching of physics (Venisari et al., 2017). This study is also aligned

with the study of Gok (2014) with the conclusion that peer instruction, one of the interactive engagement methods, had more positive effect on boys as well as girls students' conceptual learning and problem solving performance than conventional teacher-centered instruction. The results from this study are contradictory to the findings of Alemu (2020) with findings that peer-assisted strategy has no positive effect on the problem-solving skill of students and Supeno et al. (2018) whose results revealed that students' performance in scientific reasoning, problem-solving, and scientific writing skills is not satisfactory. The reasons are the lack of a control group and the number of questions which is too small, only two questions for assessing problem-solving skills are not sufficient. Furthermore, the problems are ill-structured. This study may benefit students in developing problem-solving skills when working in groups, which is an essential ingredient for enhanced academic achievement.

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